

PLACE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM

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Annotatsiya: in this article today, rapidly changing with the times, developing in the field of tourism the importance of English language English language given information about its role in the development of international tourism .

The key sozlar: tourism around the world , the English language , international language of the world population ,the development of the native language.

Annotasiya: angliyskogo yazika v o v sovremennom predstavlena V dannoy state tourism information vajnosti sfera bistro razvivayutshemsya mira angliyskogo yazika v razvitii mejdunarodnogo role in tourism.

Klyuchevie slovo: mirovoy tourism, angliyskiy yazik, mirovoe naselenie, mejdunarodniy yazik, rodnoy yazik, razrabotka.

Annotation: this article provides information about the importance of English in the field of tourism in the development of rapid developing and safely today's rolan the word in the English language of the international tourist.

Keywords: international tourism, English language, international language, world population, the morning, mother, development.

Access

Today, as in all areas of tourism development in the field of English language requirements also increased. From the experience of the world as it is known, not only remain the international language to be English, this language is the native language for half of the world's population. This is also the most spoken language around the world that have come out which is the most comprehensive and English language. The different options, and many specific features of affairs, despite being raised to the level of the English language is most popular language in the world. If it does not take the general look of the world, the major sectors, which is the area of the country known to the world economy, politics, science and technology in modern sports, the development of the international tourism industry as many was the night directly through the English language. In addition, the policy world, in the organization of interstate relations, in the integration of advanced achievements of science, international trade, transport and exchange in the process of interethnic communication, scientists, academic and science international conference, the summit of the organization of the event and state ahamiyatdagi during sports competitions between the two countries in the olympic games and all international tournaments in the global, digital technology, gadget the user appears as the most basic of the English language.

Literature review and methodology

The role of tourism that we have to look in the world of English language, this language among the population of the world in terms of the coverage are of great importance. Most countries of the world adopted this language as the official language along with English and the native language will communicate in the language. This means that while the rest of the tourists to travel with the desire to get out if he knows the English language, may establish, easy and convenient to travel to many countries of the world. Moreover, the course of transportation from one country to another country to travel by train, plane or sea of by type is selected. International air flights, and international flights in the port the service also is conducted in English. Also the majority of the type of agency conducts its activities in English. Tourism - tourism as a result of globalization, the rest of the world's population is one of the areas that needs to be developing as a result of the increase. Tourism - many areas of the economy, including transport, communication, road construction, hotel and catering, service, household service, like the cover of industry trade and directly contribute to the development of the network. Tourism is the main source of funding for some countries-bearing is not. Some countries will support the welfare of the living conditions of

their people living through tourism .Tourism in many countries of the world as a single system will bring significant revenue to the budget of developing countries . Tourism is not only one of the world's largest networks, but also on the basis of dynamic is one of the developing sector.A different approach to the definition and tourism can bring. Tourism - usually out of the rest of the environment to get to work related to education , or other social purposes not exceeding one year for business travel and places to be performed in person, given the definition says, 1991 in ottawa, held BTT - the whole world tourism organization conference . Of the republic of uzbekistan "on tourism" tourism in article 3 of the law is characterized as follows: "Tourism - the physical health of the person's permanent residence, educational, professional and practical , or for other purposes in the place go (in the country) to engage in activity in case not later than a period of one year paid departure (to travel) is . Tourism - vacations empty meaningful the time is a form of mass transfer . Tourism includes all forms of travel ,but travel also gets all type of tourism . This field in turn to the network ,including from the sports tourism ,educational tourism, social tourism ,tourism in order rekrayesiya ,exotic tourism, ecological tourism ,travel and tourism hk.

Discuss

Also in the field of tourism and foreign languages, including also the importance of the English language is incomparable. Because of this I am also a thorough master of foreign languages in the area ,there is a high demand for qualified employees . The English language is the language of most of the leading hotel and service tamoqlarining . And finally, as I mentioned in one of mqollarining people, " know the language - el knew." After all , developing tourism into a piece of zamonamiz with severe , see the world, by the way, your outlook on the world and enrich their journey out for reasons other social yuzlanmoqchi by the way ,if you want to learn the language ! This simply is not recommended ,the time demands. Tanimiqchi of many nations in the world , the news about going to the first, materials and scientific literature in the original sample to read if you're going to learn the English language for you ! And most importantly through the world as a cultural leisure for yourself , return to the country to learn the English language with new ideas if you intend to start from now on !

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